

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DEPENDENCE OF DENTAL CARIES INDICATORS IN SCHOOLCHILDREN OF TASHKENT ON THEIR PSYCHO-EMOTIONAL STRESS

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Abstract

Dental caries is one of the widespread diseases of hard dental tissues, especially in childhood. In spite of the fact, that much attention is paid to the issues of development and improvement of the methods of caries prevention, its prevalence and intensity remains high enough. Psycho-emotional, physical and intellectual stress experienced by high school students contribute to the beginning of disease development or exacerbation of chronic pathology. Along with the psycho-emotional stress, the dental health of schoolchildren suffers. Analysis of the indices estimating the state of dental hard tissues revealed a direct correlation between the prevalence and intensity of dental caries and the presence of psycho-emotional tension.

Keywords: schoolchildren, psycho-emotional stress, hygiene index, intensity and prevalence of dental caries, initial caries.

Relevance and literature review of the problem. The problem of dental caries prevention in different age groups of population is the main one in dentistry [5,12,15]. Epidemiological dental surveys carried out in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan testify to the high prevalence of dental caries among child population [1,2,3,6,13].

Development and course of dental caries largely depends on the ratio of de- and remineralization processes in subsurface enamel layers, and application of remineralizing therapy to increase resistance of dental tissues is one of the most promising ways of caries prevention [5,7,10]. Timely set of measures aimed at diagnosis and detection of focal enamel demineralization in the form of chalky stain stage and urgent implementation of a set of measures aimed at remineralization of cavity-free formations will allow to achieve delayed and possibly complete restoration of enamel integrity under certain conditions, which will prevent further progression to cavities with subsequent standard technique of restoration of lost tissues by filling [11,16,17,18], so the issues of timely diagnosis, treatment and prevention of the dental caries in schoolchildren have become of special actuality.

The period of high school education, for many persons of young age is not an easy period. At this time there is a significant psychoemotional, physical and intellectual load, which can lead to the beginning of disease development or exacerbation of chronic pathology. The problem is exacerbated in case of inattention of schoolchildren to their health, hormonal changes, bad habits, nonobservance of rest and work regime, long stay at computer screens and smartphones [4,8,12,13].

Purpose of the study: Assessment of the dental status of high school students in Tashkent depending on their psycho-emotional stress.

Material and methods: In order to achieve the set tasks we conducted a dental examination in 108 students from group I (n=56) and group II (n=52) at the age of 14-17 years in Almazar district of Tashkent.

Dental examination of athletes was carried out in a dental chair under artificial light using a traditional examination set of dental instruments, dental dye to detect plaque and 2% methylene blue solution to diagnose focal demineralization of enamel.

Psychoemotional tension in high school students was determined using a clinical questionnaire by K.K. Yakhin and D.M. Mendelevich (2005) [9,14]. Dental status was determined by indices: severity and intensity of caries using the CPE index.

Dental caries prevalence was determined as follows: the percentage of children who had at least one of the signs of dental caries manifestation (cariou, filled, teeth removed as a result of caries complications) to the total number of examined children.

The intensity of dental caries was determined individually using the CPE index of teeth, represented by the sum of cariou, filled and extracted teeth due to caries complications in one patient. Each component of the index was calculated separately: "C" - cariou tooth, "P" - filled, "E" - extracted.

Hygienic condition using OHI-S Green-Vermilion index, Identification of enamel caries in the chalk stain stage and evaluation of enamel demineralization intensity in the lesion area was carried out by the enamel vitality staining method (L.A. Aksamit, 1978). The data were statistically processed using Microsoft Office Excel computer program with parametric statistical methods.

Results of the study:

According to the indicators of the OHI-S index, the level of oral hygiene in the examined schoolchildren of Group I was 2.03 ± 0.02 , Group II - $2.31 \pm 0.05^*$, which corresponds to an unsatisfactory level of hygiene in all the examined schoolchildren. The structure of OHI-S index was dominated by the components of soft plaque and supragingival tartar, covering not more than 1/3 of the examined tooth surface. The reasons were poor hygiene, forgetfulness, lack of motivation, lack of knowledge of interdental hygiene products, prolonged use of toothbrushes, a very limited list of personal hygiene products, laziness.

According to the results of the dental examination, the most common pathology among schoolchildren is dental caries, which was detected in 74.2% of the examined schoolchildren of Group I and 89.7% of the schoolchildren of Group II. Caries in the stain stage was detected in 9 (16.1%) Group I students and 21 (40.4%) Group II students.

The prevalence of chalk stains in group I schoolchildren was 16.1% and was detected in 9 schoolchildren, the number of demineralization foci was 20, which averaged 2.2 ± 0.10 . The prevalence of chalk spots in group II was 40.4% and was revealed in 21 schoolchildren, the number of foci of demineralization was 53, the average corresponded to 2.5 ± 0.20 .

Cretaceous spots were located mainly in cervical areas of incisors and canines of frontal teeth group and were identified to the same extent on cervical surfaces of premolars and molars of both jaws. When studying the depth of enamel lesion by vitality staining with 2% methylene blue solution and subsequent evaluation by ten-field half-tone blue scale the presence of caries foci in the chalky stain stage with different degree of staining was found. Number of lesion foci with low degree of staining (1 to 3 points) was 2.32 ± 0.25 , with medium degree (4 to 5 points) - 0.1 ± 0.03 . It should be noted that in both groups I and II studied there were no schoolchildren with foci with high degree of staining (from 6 to 10 points).

Table 1

Prevalence of dental caries, focal demineralization and hygiene index in the examined groups

	Group I	Group II группа
Total examinees	56	52
OHI-S	$2,03 \pm 0,02^*$	$2,31 \pm 0,05^*$
Tooth caries	176*	244*
Including initial caries	20*	53*
Intact зубы	50	38

* - the difference is significant in comparison with the parameters of the 1st group ($p < 0,05$)

When evaluating the index CPE, its values in group I students were equal to 5.78 ± 0.24 , in group II - 8.13 ± 0.02 , differences are statistically reliable.

According to these indexes we can see that when psycho-emotional tension intensifies, carious process intensity indexes increase. In pupils of both groups components "C" and "P" prevailed in the index CPE. Significant differences in the "Y" component of the CPE index were not obtained in schoolchildren. The average number of carious teeth in the CPE index was C (carious) - 3.50 ± 1.1 ; P (filled) - 1.44 ± 0.17 ; E (extracted) - 0.84 ± 0.01 in group I of schoolchildren. The

same figures in group II of schoolchildren corresponded to C - 5.72 ± 0.23 ; P - 1.56 ± 0.15 ; E - 0.85 ± 0.01 . The need for endodontic treatment among schoolchildren in group I was 26.7% (15), in group II 40.4% [21].

Among the schoolchildren in group I the most common localization of carious cavities and fillings were cavities and fillings according to Black class II, which occurred in 67.3% of all cases. But as the level of psycho-emotional stress increased, the number of Black class V carious cavities and fillings increased in group II students, which occurred in 31.2% of cases of caries and fillings and only in 9.6% of group I students.

Table 2

Prevalence and intensity of dental caries (%) in the studied schoolchildren

Total examinees	Prevalence of tooth caries (%)	Dental caries intensity			
		CPE	C	P	E
Group 1	74,2%*	5,78±0,24*	3,50±1,1*	1,44±0,17*	0,84±0,01
Group II	89,7%*	8,13±0,02*	5,72±0,23*	1,56±0,15*	0,85±0,01

* - the difference is reliable in comparison with the parameters of the 1st group ($p < 0,05$)

The comparative analysis of the parameters of prevalence and intensity of dental caries in groups I and II testifies to reliably different results in the compared groups. In the group of schoolchildren with psycho-emotional tension there was a reliable increase in the prevalence and intensity of dental caries and in the component "C" and "P". The need for endodontic treatment among the schoolchildren with psycho-emotional tension exceeds by 1,5 times the indicators of the 1st group of schoolchildren where no psycho-emotional tension is revealed.

Thus, as a result of the carried out research the growth of dental caries morbidity has been revealed.

Conclusions: the direct correlational connection between the prevalence and intensity of dental caries and the presence of psycho-emotional tension has been revealed while studying the indices which assess the condition of the hard dental tissues. At poor hygiene of the oral cavity of all schoolchildren in the II group of investigation, the intensity and prevalence of dental caries significantly differed from the indicators of the I group.

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TREATMENT-AND-PROPHYLACTIC COMPLEX AT THE STAGES OF PROSTHETICS WITH NON-REMOVABLE ORTHOPEDIC STRUCTURES

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Abstract

Patients who used the recommendations of an orthopedist on the 4th day showed a complete absence of pain, bleeding edema and hyperemia. times faster, the hygiene indicator stably remained in the “good” interval, while in the control group the state of hygiene worsened somewhat and the “satisfactory” hygiene interval returned.

Keywords: periodontium, fixed orthopedic structures, individual oral hygiene, Sensadin therapeutic and prophylactic agents, LISTERINE® rinse

As practice has shown, in the case of partial absence of teeth, preference is given to fixed bridge structures [6]. However, the process of manufacturing non-removable orthopedic structures has its own characteristics, which will determine the preservation of the viability of the pulp, the state of periodontal tissues, retention and fixation of the prosthesis, service life, and most importantly, its aesthetic appearance [5].

One of the features of the preparation of hard tissues of the tooth for fixed orthopedic structures is the creation of a cervical ledge, especially when prosthetics of the anterior group of teeth. [3]. The ledge should ensure a smooth transition of the artificial crown to the root of the tooth and prevent injury to the edge of the mucous membrane and the intergingival papilla [1]. However, excessive grinding of hard tissues with the creation of an excessive taper of the side walls leads to trauma to the pulp and the marginal periodontium, which in the future worsens the fixation of the finished prosthesis.

The injury can be caused by a gum retraction procedure. Gingival retraction is a procedure for expanding the gingival sulcus and is necessary to obtain high-quality two-layer impressions, although gum retraction is also carried out to protect the marginal periodontium

from mechanical injury by future fixed structures. In one case or another, the retraction procedure itself leads to periodontal injury [2]. Thus, trauma to the gums during preparation and retraction is inevitable, since the quality of the future fixed orthopedic structure and the period of its use depend on these manipulations. , And the probability of occurrence of gum recession processes after a certain period of time is quite high. To prevent the development of inflammatory changes in the marginal periodontium in the area of odontopreparation, it is important to eliminate local irritating factors, to conduct high-quality professional and individual oral hygiene (IHPR). This is due to the fact that after the preparation and fixation of temporary crowns, high-quality toothbrushing in this area becomes impossible, since it causes sharp pain, and the presence of pathogenic microorganisms will aggravate the situation and aggravate the inflammatory process. orthopedic structures will be different in each case [4]. When using dental floss inserted under the edge of the crown, it is necessary to make circular movements with the floss, which contributes to a better elimination of food debris, however, the use of super floss and brushes is much more effective. After that, it is mandatory to use oral